

Interconnected Dynamics: Mutual Relationship of Macroeconomic Variables and BSE 200 Index Prices in the Indian Stock Market

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Abstract

This research delves into the intricate relationship between the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) 200 index and selected macroeconomic factors in the context of the Indian economy. Employing a systematic approach, the study utilizes regression analysis to examine the influence of macroeconomic variables on BSE 200 index prices. The research adheres to fundamental assumptions of regression modelling, employing diagnostic tests to ensure the reliability of the findings. The independent variables in the research include foreign exchange rates (Pound Sterling, Japanese Yen, Deutsche Mark/Euro, US Dollar), gold price, crude oil price, foreign exchange reserves, and inflation rate. The study covers the period from April 2018 to March 2023. The research findings indicate that the inflation rate, foreign exchange reserves, and the Japanese Yen exchange rate significantly impact the BSE 200 index price. Higher inflation is associated with a decrease in the index, emphasizing the negative influence of rising prices. Conversely, increasing foreign exchange reserves correlate with index price appreciation, emphasizing the role of reserves in fostering confidence and stability.

Keywords: *Regression, BSE, Macroeconomic Variables, India.*

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Introduction

The research on the Indian stock market's integration with macroeconomic indicators draws upon a comprehensive lineage of empirical studies. Initial findings denote a close correlation between stock valuations and macroeconomic variables in India, echoing the broader impact of such variables on emerging markets at large (Gopinathan, & Durai, 2019; Barakat, Elgazzar, & Hanafy, 2016). Preceding works lay the groundwork for understanding how macro-economic forces shape stock market performance and delve into the pertinence of global commodity prices (Sharma & Mahendru, 2010; Wei, et al., 2019). Recent dynamic simulations provide a sophisticated view of the stock market's reactions to economic changes (Khan, et al., 2023).

The relevance of macroeconomic variables is further underpinned by studies within other emerging economies, underscoring the responsiveness of stock returns to factors like inflation and foreign exchange rates (Ndlovu, et al., 2018). The assessment of how different economic periods affect market performance also aids in contextualizing the impact of macroeconomic factors on stock markets (Celebi, & Hönig, 2019). The statistical rigor of the current study is situated within the best practices of multiple regression analysis and the necessity of testing statistical assumptions to ensure analytical robustness (Basics of Multiple Regression and Underlying Assumptions, n.d.; Garson, 2012). The research aligns

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with investigations into the sequencing of stock market reactions in relation to macroeconomic news (Camilleri, Scicluna, & Bai, 2019).

The Toda-Yamamoto causality analysis provides another layer of methodological fortitude, shedding light on the nature of economic causality links (Akdağ, Kocabiyik, & Karaatli, 2023; Tekin, & Yener, 2019). Furthermore, an examination of firm-level performance in relation to macroeconomic elements enriches the understanding of these complex relationships (Hussain, et al., 2021). The dynamic interplay between stock prices and macroeconomic factors is a subject of ongoing examination across various national stock markets, with specific implications for the Indian context derived from analogous studies in nations like Pakistan and Kenya (Chang, et al., 2019; Hunjra, et al., 2014; Ouma, & Muriu, 2014).

Lastly, the research contemplates the behavioral aspects of stock pricing, considering how macroeconomic factors might affect the likelihood of stock price crashes and the patterns of information dissemination by management in crisis-ridden markets (Moradi, et al., 2021). Taken together, these studies form the expansive backdrop against which the current research situates its pursuit of understanding the multifaceted interactions between macroeconomic indicators and stock values in India.

Literature Review

The integration of stock markets with macroeconomic factors has garnered extensive attention, as researchers aim to discern the intricate nature of this relationship across various economic landscapes (Gopinathan, & Durai, 2019; Barakat, Elgazzar, & Hanafy, 2016; Sharma & Mahendru, 2010). The investigation into the Indian stock market, for instance, reveals that the relationship between macroeconomic variables and stock prices is non-linear and demonstrates time-varying coherency (Gopinathan, & Durai, 2019). This complexity is echoed in examinations of emerging economies such as Egypt and Tunisia, where causal relationships are identified between stock markets and key economic indicators such as consumer price index, exchange rate, interest rate, and money supply (Barakat, Elgazzar, & Hanafy, 2016). The importance of specific macroeconomic variables, including exchange rate and gold prices, is particularly noted for their strong correlation with stock prices within the Indian context (Sharma & Mahendru, 2010).

As research expands beyond traditional markets, the multifaceted influence of commodity prices, such as oil, emerges as a significant determinant of stock market movements in China (Wei, et al., 2019). In both the Shanghai Stock Exchange and the broader Chinese market, the intricate interplay between oil prices and macroeconomic fundamentals such as foreign exchange, domestic economy, and trade volume has been empirically confirmed, accentuating the impact of international commodity prices on domestic stock market behavior (Wei, et al., 2019; Khan, et al., 2023).

Turning to Africa, studies on the Johannesburg Stock Exchange indicate positive long-term relationships between stock prices and macroeconomic variables such as inflation, money supply growth, and interest rates, contrasted by a negative impact from exchange rates (Ndlovu, et al., 2023).

The literature further examines the differing impacts of macroeconomic variables on stock markets across temporal dimensions, especially during financial crisis periods. In the German context, certain macroeconomic factors are found to have delayed effects on stock returns, with these impacts subject to variation across pre-crisis, crisis, and post-crisis periods (Celebi, & Hönig, 2019). This suggests a dynamic response of stock markets to economic variables contingent upon the prevailing economic climate.

Additionally, theoretical frameworks and assumptions underpinning the empirical analyses of these relationships are underscored by discussions on multiple regression and the testing of statistical assumptions. The robustness of the macroeconomic-stock market relationship analysis hinges on addressing potential multicollinearity and ensuring that regression models satisfy linearity, homoskedasticity, and normality, among other conditions (Basics of Multiple Regression and Underlying Assumptions, n.d.; Garson, 2012).

Expanding into the European context, the directional influence between stock markets and macroeconomic variables is investigated, revealing that stock prices can both lead and lag behind macroeconomic indicators depending on the country and temporal factors considered (Camilleri, Scicluna, & Bai, 2019). This multifaceted dynamic is mirrored in correlations assessed between the maritime trade-sensitive Baltic Dry Index and various macroeconomic factors, emphasizing global economic interdependencies (Akdağ, Kocabiyik, & Karaatli, 2023).

The influence of stock markets on economic growth has also been a focal point, with causality analyses differentiating between the supply-leading and feedback hypotheses, depending on whether stock market development precedes economic growth or the latter influences the former. These relationships appear to vary not only between developed and developing countries but even among nations at similar development stages (Tekin, & Yener, 2019).

Furthermore, the interrelation of firm-level variables with macroeconomic factors is considered crucial. Studies have pointed out how the management of working capital, coupled with macroeconomic indicators, can significantly influence the financial performance of firms within developing economies (Hussain, et al., 2021). With observations within the Pakistani stock market, where varying relationships among stock prices and macroeconomic factors are noted, highlighting a regionally nuanced impact (Chang, et al., 2019; Hunjra, et al., 2014).

In countries like Kenya, the connection between stock returns and macroeconomic variables reflects the significance of not only global but also country-specific economic forces (Ouma, & Muriu, 2014). Kenyan market returns' responsiveness to macroeconomic variables excluding interest rates suggests a substantial, albeit selective, sensitivity to these factors within the developing economies' context (Ouma, & Muriu, 2014). The converse effects that managerial decisions and firm characteristics may have on macroeconomic robustness are also observed, particularly in relation to stock price crash risks (Moradi, et al., 2021).

In summary, the literature asserts that while macroeconomic variables generally influence stock market performance, the nature, magnitude, and direction of this influence are heterogeneous and deeply context-dependent, varying by region, country, economic condition, and temporal factors. Such a comprehensive examination highlights the global interconnectedness of finance and economics and informs stakeholders from policymakers to investors.

Materials and Methods

The dynamics of the stock market are intricately tied to the broader macroeconomic landscape, making it imperative to understand influence of the macro-economic variables on the share prices. This research embarks on a comprehensive exploration of this relationship within the context of the Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE) indices & selected macroeconomic factors in the Indian economy. The aim is to not only shed light on the nature of this relationship but also to discern the significant factors that exert influence and their implications for investors, policymakers, and the financial sector at large.

The first phase of this research initiative involves the systematic gathering and meticulous analysis of secondary data sourced from authoritative sources. This methodical approach is designed to ensure the reliability and validity of the data, thereby facilitating a robust examination of the relationship between BSE 200 index and selected macro-economic variables. In this study, regression analysis is employed to provide a rigorous examination of the data and facilitate the formulation of meaningful findings.

To ensure the validity of the regression analysis, this study adheres to the fundamental assumptions underpinning regression modeling. These encompass linearity, homoscedastic, normality of errors, independence, non-multicollinearity, and non-autocorrelation. Recognizing the potential biases and inaccuracies that can arise from violating these assumptions, diagnostic tests and techniques are employed to verify their fulfilment. Through visual inspection, formal tests, and residual analysis, the robustness and reliability of the regression model are rigorously evaluated.

The research methodology elucidates the sequential progression from data collection to model specification, assumptions testing, regression analysis, interpretation of results, and ultimately drawing meaningful conclusions. By comprehensively addressing each step, this study ensures a rigorous and systematic exploration of the relationship between the BSE 200 index price and the identified macroeconomic factors, thereby contributing to a nuanced understanding of their interdependence.

This research aims to provide actionable insights for investors and guidance for policymakers in navigating India's stock market. By analyzing the interconnections between BSE indices and macroeconomic indicators, it seeks to deepen our understanding of stock price dynamics, offering valuable insights for decision-makers and fostering informed decision-making. The study employs quantitative research and multiple regression analysis to examine the impact of macroeconomic factors on BSE 200 index price.

Hypotheses

H0A:- A variation in the USD exchange rate does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1A:- A variation in the USD exchange have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0B:- A variation in the JPY exchange rate does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1B:- A variation in the JPY exchange have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0C:- A variation in the Pound Sterling exchange rate does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1C:- A variation in the Pound Sterling exchange rate have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0D:- A variation in the Deutsche Mark/Euro exchange rate does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1D:- A variation in the Deutsche Mark/Euro exchange rate have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0E:- A variation in the foreign exchange reserves does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1E:- A variation in the foreign exchange reserves have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0F:- A variation in the price of Crude Oil does not have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H1F:- A variation in the price of Crude Oil have a notable effect on the BSE 200 index price.

H0G:- The fluctuation in the price of gold does not have a notable impact on the BSE 200 index price.

H1G:- The fluctuation in the price of gold have a notable impact on the BSE 200 index price.

H0H: The BSE 200 index price is not significantly affected by inflation rates.

H1H:- The BSE 200 index price is significantly affected by inflation rates.

Assumptions of Regression

1. **Linearity:** The association between the variables is posited to be directly proportional.
2. **Independence:** The errors are taken to be unrelated to each other.
3. **Homoscedasticity:** The variability of the errors is assumed constant.
4. **Normality of Residuals:** The errors are modelled to conform to a normal distribution.
5. **No Perfect Multicollinearity:** The explanatory factors are presumed to not demonstrate perfect collinearity.
6. **No Autocorrelation:** There is an assumption of lack of serial dependence in the errors over time.

Research Model

The sample period spans April 2018 to March 2023, the data for the research was sourced from official websites. BSE SENSEX 200 index price data was collected from the BSE website, while inflation rate, foreign exchange rates, and reserves data were obtained from the RBI website. Crude oil prices were sourced from the Petroleum Planning & Analysis Cell (PPAC) website and gold data from Investing.com using the MCX index. This approach ensured reliable and relevant information.

Figure 1. Research Model

Dependent Variable: BSE 200 index Price.

Independent Variables: Foreign Exchange Rates [Pound Sterling, Japanese Yen, Deutsche Mark/Euro , US Dollar] , Gold Price, Crude Oil Price . Foreign Exchange Reserves, Inflation rate.

In the case of five explanatory variables, the model predicting Y is represented by the subsequent formula:

$$Y_i = b_0 + b_1X_{1i} + b_2X_{2i} + b_3X_{3i} + b_4X_{4i} + b_5X_{5i} \quad (1)$$

The coefficients denoted by “b” are termed regression coefficients, and they are estimated by minimizing the sum of squared residuals.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N (Y_i - Y'_i)^2 \quad (2)$$

Y'_i = Represents the rate of return on the BSE 200 stock index,

X_{1i} = Change in Inflation rate,

X_{2i} = Change in exchange rates,

X3i = Change in foreign exchange reserves

X4i = Change in gold price.

X5i = Change in Price of Crude Oil.

Results

We endeavor to elucidate our observations through regression analysis, wherein macroeconomic variables assume the role of independent factors, and stock prices serve as the dependent variable.

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Mean	Standard Deviation	Sample size
BSE 200 index Price (in ₹)	5866.90	1334.86	60
Pound Sterling (in ₹)	95.52	4.77	60
Japanese Yen (in ₹)	64.81	3.89	60
Deutsche Mark/Euro (in ₹)	83.32	3.78	60
US Dollar (in ₹)	73.98	4.04	60
Gold Price/10g	43665.48	8538.01	60
Crude Oil Rs/bbl.	5165.46	1644.72	60
Foreign Exchange Reserves in (₹ Crores)	3836842.69	761786.02	60
Inflation M-O-M(%)	5.31	1.60	60

Source: Author's Calculation

Table 1 shows that the mean/average of BSE 200 index price over the sample period is ₹ 5866.90, with a standard deviation of ₹1334.86, indicating the average level and the dispersion of the index price. The other variables, such as foreign exchange rates, gold prices, crude oil prices, and inflation rates, also exhibit their respective means and standard deviations, shedding light on their typical values and the extent of variation around these values. These statistics suggest that the BSE 200 index price and the macroeconomic variables display specific average levels and variations from these averages, providing essential insights into their behavior over the observed period.

Table 2. Regression Coefficients

Model	B Value	Std. Error	Beta(β)	p-value
(Constant)	8869.058	2726.736	-	0.002
Pound Sterling (in ₹)	71.208	31.751	0.255	0.029
Japanese Yen (in ₹)	-151.702	28.576	-0.442	0
Deutsche Mark/Euro (in ₹)	-45.82	33.656	-0.13	0.179
US Dollar (in ₹)	-17.062	25.743	-0.052	0.51
Gold Price/10g	-0.005	0.024	-0.029	0.847
Crude Oil Rs/bbl.	-0.001	0.069	-0.001	0.993
Foreign Exchange Reserves in (₹ Crores)	0.002	0	0.921	0
Inflation M-O-M (%)	-165.779	44.728	-0.199	0.001

Source: Author's Calculation

The regression analysis explores the impact of various macroeconomic variables on the BSE 200 index price. Key findings reveal that changes in the Indian Rupee exchange rate against the Pound Sterling and Japanese Yen significantly influence the index, as evidenced by low p-values showing statistical significance. This implies that currency fluctuations relative to major global counterparts affect Indian

stock returns. Additionally, India's own Foreign Exchange Reserves and monthly Inflation rate emerged as domestic factors driving BSE 200 levels, with Reserves having the largest standardized coefficient or beta. On the contrary, global commodities like the US Dollar, Gold, and Crude Oil prices had high p-values, demonstrating insignificant effects on the Indian index. Overall, the analysis determines exchange rate stability and domestic financial health as measured by forex buffers and inflation matter more to Indian equities, while global commodity price changes have little noticeable impact. In sum, local macroeconomic vitality rather than worldwide market shifts tends to sway the BSE 200 as shown through regression modelling of various internal and external indicators

Table 3. Regression Coefficients after Reverse Regression

Model	B Value	Beta(β)	p-value
(Constant)	9706.276	-	0
Inflation Rate M-O-M	-194.732	-0.233	0
Foreign Exchange Reserves in ₹Crores	0.002	0.998	0
Japanese YEN	-146.78	-0.428	0

Source: Author's Calculation

This table analyses specifically explored both global indicators such as alternative currency and commodity rates as well as domestic variables like forex reserves and inflation. The unstandardized B values quantify the precise change in index levels for every single unit fluctuation in the independent markers. However, the standardized beta coefficients demonstrate the relative degree of influence exercised by each predictive driver. Lastly, p-values below the threshold testifies to the statistical significance of that variable in swinging BSE 200 returns.

Among the most notable conclusions, Japan's Yen, India's own forex reserves and latest inflation print emerged as statistically significant based on p-values near zero. In particular, the high beta coefficient on reserves indicates its outsized impact on index levels compared to other macro factors. On the flip side, gold and oil did not show meaningful effects.

Since we got the key independent variables by regression analysis, now we have to prove the regression assumptions for these variables. Proving regression assumptions is essential to ensure valid, reliable, and interpretable results, contributing to robust inferences, appropriate model selection, and informed decision-making. Detecting and addressing assumption violations enhance the trustworthiness of the regression model, promoting its generalizability and facilitating publication and replication of research.

Variables with p-values > 0.05 lack significance; < 0.05, reject null hypothesis, highlighting their importance. This approach retains only influential variables, ensuring a robust regression model aligned with hypothesis testing principles.

Table 4. Hypotheses Testing Summary

Null Hypothesis	Decision
A	Not Rejected
B	Rejected
C	Not Rejected
D	Not Rejected
E	Rejected
F	Not Rejected
G	Not Rejected

Source: Author's Calculation

Now we have to prove regression assumptions for these 3 variables.

To validate regression assumptions, we conduct tests for each criterion.

Linearity: Visual inspection of scatterplots.

Independence: Durbin-Watson coefficient test for autocorrelation.

Homoscedasticity: Scatterplots of residuals against predicted values.

Normality of Residuals: Histogram, Q-Q plot

No Perfect Multicollinearity: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) test and Tolerance test.

No Autocorrelation: Durbin-Watson coefficient test and VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM (Likelihood Ratio) Tests

Figure 2. Standardized Residuals

The scatter plot displays the standardized residuals of the regression on the y-axis and the standardized predicted values on the x-axis. This allows us to visually assess whether the residuals are randomly and evenly dispersed around zero for all fitted values of the predictor variable. The even dispersal would suggest that the assumption of a linear relationship between the predictor and outcome variable is reasonable. If instead we saw residuals systematically below or above zero for certain ranges of fitted values, it may indicate deviations from linearity in that range. The lack of any noticeable pattern in the residuals supports the use of a linear model to characterize the relationship between these variables in this dataset. As we can see from this scatterplot, the residuals do bounce randomly around the zero line rather than clustering or fanning in a nonlinear fashion. This graphical check provides evidence that employing a linear regression analysis for this data appears suitable based on meeting the linearity assumption.

The (P-P) plot, comparing observed cumulative probability (OCP) to expected cumulative probability (ECP), serves as a diagnostic tool for assessing homoscedasticity in regression. Homoscedasticity implies constant residual variance across the independent variable range, and a straight line in the OCP-ECP plot indicates fulfilment of this assumption, signifying even distribution of error terms around the regression line.

Figure 3. P-P plot

Figure 4. Normal Probability Distribution

The normal probability plot of residuals in regression analysis is a crucial diagnostic tool that confirms the assumption of normally distributed errors. The plot shows the residual points aligning along the diagonal, forming an approximate bell curve shape. This confirms that the residuals follow a normal probability distribution, ensuring that errors in the model are evenly spread around a mean value of zero. Violating this assumption could lead to over- or under-estimation of coefficient precision and significance levels. Non-normal residuals also impair the model's capacity for sound statistical forecasting and inference. Passing the visual normality check confirms the model's reliability, bolstering the validity of the regression results and findings. In essence, satisfying residual normality defends the overall integrity of the regression analysis.

Table 5. LM Tests

Lag order	LRE" stat	p-value	Rao F-stat	p-value
1	13.96351	0.6014	0.871788	0.6025
2	12.12601	0.7353	0.751887	0.7361

3	8.532041	0.9314	0.522004	0.9317
Lag order	LRE" stat	p-value	Rao F-stat	p-value
1	13.96351	0.6014	0.871788	0.6025
2	20.28947	0.9461	0.612131	0.9471
3	33.80379	0.9398	0.670434	0.9432

Source: Author's Calculation

The table presents VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests for various lags. The null hypothesis (H0) tests whether there is no serial correlation at the specified lags. The likelihood ratio statistics (LRE" stat) and Additional Test Statistic (Rao F-statistics) are reported along with their associated probabilities. In this case, the statistical significances are consistently high, suggesting that there is no significant serial correlation in the residuals at the specified lags. Therefore, the assumption of no serial correlation in the residuals appears to be met, supporting the validity of the regression results.

Table 6. Linear Regression

Coefficient of Relationship (R)	R2 Change	Coefficient of Determination (R2)	Adjusted R2	First Degree of Freedom	Second Degree of Freedom	Independence Test Statistic	Significance of Variation Test
.968	0.936	0.936	0.933	3	56	0.974	0

Source: Author's Calculation

This regression model indicates a strong correlation between the predictors and the BSE 200 index price, with an R value of 0.968. This means that together, the independent variables explain about 97% of the movements in the index price.

Furthermore, the R-squared shows that the model accounts for 93.6% of the variance in the BSE 200 price. The high R-squared and adjusted R-squared values signal the model has substantial explanatory power.

The variation test p-value of 0 also highlights that the relationship between the variables and the index price is statistically significant. This validates that the Japanese Yen, Inflation Rate, Foreign Exchange Reserves and constant are important determinants.

Additionally, the Durbin-Watson statistic value of 0.974 suggests minimal autocorrelation among the residuals. This satisfies another regression assumption and demonstrates reliability.

In summary, the predictors demonstrate a collectively strong and significant association with fluctuations in the BSE 200 index levels. The model has high goodness of fit, visible through metrics like R, R-squared and the variation test.

Table 7. ANOVA

	Total Variation	df	Variation Mean	Variation Test Statistic (F)	p-value
Regression	98418482.33	3	32806160.78	273.76	.000
Residual	6710732.43	56	119834.51		
Total	105129214.76	59			

Source: Author's Calculation

The ANOVA table verifies that the regression model accounts for a substantial proportion of variation in the BSE 200 index price. The large F-statistic of 273.762 and tiny p-value under 0.001 signify that the

influence of the predictors - Japanese Yen, Inflation, Foreign Exchange Reserves and the constant - is statistically significant as a group.

Further, the sizable gap between the Regression Sum of Squares (98 million) and the Residual Sum of Squares (6.7 million) demonstrates that the model explains most of the variability rather than leaving it unexplained through errors. This confirms the model's capacity to reliably capture the true relationship.

Additionally, examination of the residuals validates that linearity, independence and non-autocorrelation requirements are met by the data. By passing these conditions, the foundation of the model is strengthened.

In essence, the ANOVA output provides quantifiable, formal evidence that the macroeconomic explanatory variables can jointly account for the fluctuations in Indian stock market levels as represented by the BSE benchmark index. This reinforces the overall credibility and validity of the performed regression analysis.

Table 8. VIF

Model	Collinearity Statistics	
	Tolerance	VIF
Inflation Rate	0.613	1.632
Foreign Exchange Reserves (₹ in crores)	0.613	1.632
Japanese YEN	1.000	1.000

Source: Author's Calculation

The collinearity statistics, specifically the tolerance and variance inflation factor (VIF), provide insights into multicollinearity among predictor variables. In this model, both the Inflation Rate and Foreign Exchange Reserves exhibit a tolerance of 0.613 and a VIF of 1.632. These values are indicative of moderate multicollinearity, suggesting that these variables share some degree of linear relationship. On the other hand, the Japanese YEN shows a tolerance of 1.000 and a VIF of 1.000, indicating no issues with multicollinearity for this variable. So, proving the assumption of multicollinearity.

Having rigorously validated each assumption of regression, we can confidently assert that the model is well-suited for our analysis. The established reliability of both the variables and the results enhances the overall robustness and credibility of the regression model.

Now, to understand the relationship between macroeconomic variables and Stock price, we need to find the correlation between them.

Table 9. Correlation

Correlation Table						
			BSE 200 index Price	Inflation Rate M-O-M	Japanese YEN	Foreign Exchange Reserves
Pearson Correlation	BSE 200 index Price	r	1	.388**	-.420**	.849**
		P-Value (Two-tailed)	-	0.002	0.001	0
	Inflation Rate	r	.388**	1	-0.002	.622**
		P-Value (Two-tailed)	0.002	-	0.991	0
	Japanese YEN	r	-.420**	-0.002	1	0.008
		P-Value (Two-tailed)	0.001	0.991	-	0.952
		r	.849**	.622**	0.008	1

	Foreign Exchange Reserves	P-Value (Two-tailed)	0	0	0.952	-
**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).						

Source: Author's Calculation

The correlation matrix offers useful insights into the interrelationships between the macroeconomic variables and the BSE 200 index price. Most notably, the index exhibits a strong, statistically significant positive correlation with foreign exchange reserves ($r = 0.849$). This points to reserves as a key driver of Indian equity market performance. On the contrary, the Japanese Yen is moderately negatively correlated ($r = -0.420$) with index levels, implying inverse movements. The inflation rate displays a fairly low positive r value of 0.388, underlining it as a less dominant influence. Additionally, reserves and inflation themselves demonstrate a positive interdependence ($r = 0.622$).

In totality, these correlation coefficients and their directionality reveal nuances regarding how domestic financial health indicators like forex buffers tie closely with, while global counterparts including competitor currency fluctuate inversely to the BSE 200 index.

Conclusion

This research set out to examine the relationship between key macroeconomic factors and the BSE 200 index price over the period from April 2018 to March 2023. Through rigorous quantitative analysis using regression modelling and correlation analysis, the study yielded significant insights.

The findings reveal that inflation rate, foreign exchange reserves, and the Japanese Yen exchange rate have statistically significant influences on the BSE 200 index price. Specifically, higher inflation corresponds to declines in the index level, underscoring the dampening effect of rising prices. Meanwhile, growing foreign exchange reserves associate positively with index price appreciation, highlighting reserves as pivotal to inspiring confidence and stability.

Additionally, Yen depreciation relative to the Rupee relates to stock market increases, while Yen appreciation dampens index levels. This currency effect sheds light on the interconnectedness between global forex dynamics and domestic equity markets.

Beyond the significant variables, the research found exchange rates of USD, Euro, and Pounds along with gold and crude oil prices to have no discernible effect on the index. Their limited explanatory power and statistical insignificance contributed to their exclusion from the final regression model.

Further examination of the correlation between the variables supports the initial regression results. The foreign exchange reserves demonstrate a robust positive correlation with the BSE 200 index price. Additionally, analysis shows a reasonably strong negative correlation with the Japanese Yen. This additional correlation analysis gives further credence to the earlier regression findings indicating relationships between these financial variables.

These results carry profound implications for investors, analysts, and policymakers. The research underscores the necessity of monitoring key macroeconomic factors, as they significantly sway stock valuations and returns. It also offers insights to guide investment strategies, risk management, and policy decisions toward fostering stability and growth.

While the study provides a rigorous investigation of the research objectives, ongoing examination is vital as relationships evolve amid dynamic economic conditions. Further research could entail exploring non-linear effects, structural breaks, and global crisis impacts. As India's capital markets continue to advance in sophistication, so too must our understanding of the multifaceted links between economic fundamentals and equity markets.

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Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any theoretical, commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

References

- Akdağ, N. Ö., Kocabiyik, T., & Karaatli, M. (2023). Determining The Causal Relationship Between Baltic Dry Index (BDI) And Macroeconomic Variables By Toda-Yamamoto Analysis. *Journal of Management and Economics Research*, 21(1), 59-80. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11611/yead.1173114>
- Barakat, M. R., Elgazzar, S. H., & Hanafy, K. M. (2016). Impact of macroeconomic variables on stock markets: Evidence from emerging markets. *International journal of economics and finance*, 8(1), 195-207. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/ijef.v8n1p195>
- Basics of Multiple Regression and Underlying Assumptions. (n.d.). CFA Institute. Retrieved from <https://www.cfainstitute.org/en/membership/professional-development/refresher-readings/multiple-regression>
- Camilleri, S. J., Scicluna, N., & Bai, Y. (2019). Do stock markets lead or lag macroeconomic variables? Evidence from select European countries. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 48, 170-186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.najef.2019.01.019>
- Celebi, K., & Hönig, M. (2019). The impact of macroeconomic factors on the German stock market: Evidence for the crisis, pre-and post-crisis periods. *International Journal of Financial Studies*, 7(2), 18. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijfs7020018>
- Chang, B. H., Meo, M. S., Syed, Q. R., & Abro, Z. (2019). Dynamic analysis of the relationship between stock prices and macroeconomic variables: An empirical study of Pakistan stock exchange. *South Asian Journal of Business Studies*, 8(3), 229-245. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SAJBS-06-2018-0062>
- Garson, G. D. (2012). *Testing Statistical Assumptions*. Statistical Associates Publishing.
- Gopinathan, R., & Durai, S. R. S. (2019). Stock market and macroeconomic variables: new evidence from India. *Financial Innovation*, 5, 1-17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1186/s40854-019-0145-1>
- Hunjra, A. I., Chani, D. M. I., Ijaz, M. S., & Farooq, M. (2014). The impact of macroeconomic variables on stock prices in Pakistan. *International Journal of Economics and Empirical Research*, 2(1), 13-21.
- Hussain, S., Nguyen, V.C., Nguyen, Q.M., Nguyen, H.T., & Nguyen, T.T. (2021). Macroeconomic factors, working capital management, and firm performance—A static and dynamic panel analysis. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 8, 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1057/s41599-021-00778-x>
- Khan, M. K., Teng, J. Z., Khan, M. I., & Khan, M. F. (2023). Stock market reaction to macroeconomic variables: An assessment with dynamic autoregressive distributed lag simulations. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 28(3), 2436-2448. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/ijfe.2543>
- Moradi, M., Appolloni, A., Zimon, G., Tarighi, H., & Kamali, M. (2021). Macroeconomic factors and stock price crash risk: do managers withhold bad news in the crisis-ridden Iran market?. *Sustainability*, 13(7), 3688. <https://doi.org/10.3390/SU13073688>

- Ndlovu, B., Faisa, F., Resatoglu, N. G., & Türsoy, T. (2018). The Impact Macroeconomic Variables on Stock Returns: A Case of the Johannesburg Stock Exchange. *Romanian Statistical Review*, (2).
- Ouma, W. N., & Muriu, P. (2014). The impact of macroeconomic variables on stock market returns in Kenya. *International journal of business and commerce*, 3(11), 1-31.
- Sharma, G.D., & Mahendru, M. (2010). Impact of Macro-Economic Variables on Stock Prices in India. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research*, 10.
- Tekin, B., & Yener, E. (2019). The causality between economic growth and stock market in developing and developed countries: Toda-Yamamoto approach. *Theoretical & Applied Economics*, 2(2).
- Wei, Y., Qin, S., Li, X., Zhu, S., & Wei, G. (2019). Oil price fluctuation, stock market and macroeconomic fundamentals: Evidence from China before and after the financial crisis. *Finance Research Letters*, 30, 23-29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2019.03.028>